

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

INTEGRATION OF MICROSERVICES ARCHITECTURE IN MICROCONTROLLER-BASED INTERNET OF THINGS SYSTEMS

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ABSTRACT

Microservices offer a method for designing and developing robust and scalable software systems. Despite the differences in their focus, Internet of Things systems have similar requirements to microservices architecture, which makes application of microservices beneficial in the field. This paper proposes a novel approach to address the problem of application of microservices in Internet of Things systems built on microcontroller-based devices. This approach is based on virtualization and clusterization of microcontrollers over network and has several advantages over traditional bare-metal development methods for microcontrollers.

Keywords: microservices, microcontroller, internet of things.

Introduction

The development and implementation of microservices architecture has changed the approach to the software development process and made great contributions. The monolithic architecture, widely used in software development earlier, nowadays mostly replaced in favor of microservice architecture. The transition to microservices architecture is intensifying day by day even in software products where earlier versions were developed with monolithic architecture. Although the application of microservice architecture found its way in Internet of Things systems, such systems mostly use Raspberry Pi and similar single-board computers, instead of microcontrollers. Because the principles of microservice architecture conflict with some of the design principles and limitations of traditional microcontroller systems, there is a need for adaptation before its application. In this study, a novel approach and new methodology proposed for the integration of microservices architecture in microcontroller-based IoT systems.

Problem statement

For the proper implementation of the microservice architecture, it is important to correctly apply its main principles for the targeted system [1]. In microcontroller-based IoT systems, it is currently not efficient to apply the microservice architecture as it is. The fact that microcontrollers have limited hardware resources and the requirement to work with limited

power reserve requires us to adapt the microservice architecture with the limitations of the microcontrollers before implementing it [2]. In this case, it is not appropriate to solve the problems of resource limitation and energy reserve, as these are expected in any microcontroller-based system. In case of a need for more computational power without energy limitations, it is more appropriate to use System-on-a-Chip (SoC) based designs, such as single-board computers, instead of microcontrollers. It is important to keep in mind that microcontroller-based devices should be small and able to work with minimal energy reserves [3]. Therefore, integration of microservices architecture in microcontroller-based IoT systems requires new approaches.

Integration of microservices in microcontrollers

The main difference between the microservice architecture from the monolithic architecture is that, although it is more complex to operate the software developed with this approach, it is more convenient to increase its scale and provide technical support in the long run [4]. In a monolithic architecture, all components of software are integrated and work as a single unit, while in microservice architecture, each component of software is divided into small and independent services that communicate with each other (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Structure of monolithic and microservice architectures

There are couple of key principles behind microservices architecture:

- each microservice should focus on a single task, which have a well-defined purpose within the larger ecosystem;
- microservices must communicate with each other over a well-defined standard interface;
- microservices should be able to work independently;
- microservices must be able to properly terminate processes and return to the operational state as quickly as possible when encountering any problems;
- microservices should log important events to facilitate monitoring and debugging.

Following these principles is important for effectively implementing a microservice architecture that promotes scalability, modularity, resilience, and maintainable codebase within the distributed systems. There are two approaches that can be used together to solve previously mentioned problems and make the microservice architecture applicable to microcontrollers in IoT systems:

- clustering of microcontrollers as in traditional computer servers and management of these clusters by a centralized network

- distribution of services by implementing each service in a separate microcontroller or in different cores of the same microcontroller

Achieving these goals separately don't offer any significancy in their own. Applying simple physical clustering does not provide any real advantage, as it is preferable to use a multi-core microcontroller or SoC rather than combining several microcontrollers. Distribution of services between independent microcontrollers also has no advantages by itself, as if we are building a multiple projects with monolithic architecture instead of applying microservice architecture, making things harder to develop and maintain. However, by combining both of these goals it is possible to achieve the correct and efficient implementation of microservices in microcontroller-based IoT systems, as this hybrid approach can optimize performance while maintaining scalability and flexibility. To implement this hybrid approach, microcontroller must be connected to a cluster network through a specific communication protocol, and coordinated by one of the devices located in this network. Thus, microcontrollers that are not physically located on the same board can behave as a cluster (Fig. 2).

Figure 2. Structure of microservices in a microcontroller-based Internet of Things system

Microcontrollers can use communication protocols such as UART, I2C, SPI, LIN, CAN between themselves, and Ethernet or Wi-Fi for communication with other devices. This eliminates need for external hardware for all microcontrollers, limiting extra costs, device size and energy consumption. These microcontrollers aren't required to be individual components in the system and can be a part of an IoT device, controlling its functionality. However, if the microcontroller is only running microservices, it wouldn't be able to perform the main tasks of the device it is a part of. Here, the main task refers to the functionality of the device where the microcontroller is

located. So there should be a scheduling mechanism that allows for both handling device functionality and running services assigned to the microcontroller (Fig. 3). This shouldn't be done using manual scheduling, as such an approach would have a noticeable negative impact on the development process. Callback or interrupt-based scheduling can be used for running services while having minimalistic effects on the source code. A combination of different scheduling methods with a hybrid approach can be used to have more control over the source code or computing resources, depending on the functionality and behavior of the device.

Figure 3. Microcontroller handling service without preventing device operation

This type of integration would require implementing a custom virtualized service runtime that can easily be used as a library while developing firmware for the device, providing flexibility without interrupting important device functionality. With this approach, each microcontroller can run a microservice while also performing the main task carried out by the device it is located on, enabling effective implementation of microservice architecture for

microcontrollers and microcontroller-based IoT systems.

Currently, the leading solutions for containerized development based on microservice architecture are Docker and Kubernetes. Docker specializes in bundling software packages with all their dependencies into portable units known as containers. Kubernetes orchestrates and manages these containers to provide efficient operation across distributed environments. These technologies rely on low-level container tools

such as “runC” to spawn and run containers. “runC” relies on the Linux kernel providing certain capabilities, such as “cgroups” and “namespaces”. Most microcontrollers don’t run operating systems, and the ones running RTOS don’t provide such advanced capabilities for container runtimes. Hence, these technologies cannot work with the limited resources of microcontrollers. As there is no wide-spread container technology available for microcontrollers, there is a need to create a new low-level container format, which requires custom implementation for the application area [5]. This can be both beneficial and risky for reliability and security. One of the most serious problems with the traditional “bare-metal programming” approach is that the security of the system can be neglected during software development. As a result, vulnerabilities in developed software can put the entire system at risk. However, there are various programming methodologies to prevent such situations [6]. Implementation of new container formats for microcontrollers should not open any doors to new potential vulnerabilities. Also, as IoT devices need to connect to a network of devices, any network-based API (“Application Programming Interface”) should be encrypted to prevent attacks such as Man-In-The-Middle (MITM). To save computation power and energy in microcontrollers, symmetric encryption algorithms could be used after exchanging encryption keys over public-key cryptography. Various methods and approaches have also been proposed for the safety and risk analysis of System-on-a-Chip and microcontrollers in life-critical systems. Application of these methodologies can slow down the process of developing software for microcontrollers; however, they can be beneficial in the long term to prevent potential backdoors [7]. Currently, there are tools available for both traditional software and microcontroller systems that analyze software sources and detect potential vulnerabilities and problems. Such tools are called static analysis tools, and they can be useful to find issues without lengthening the software development process. Static analysis tools can report initial gaps in the source code during development; however, they are not suitable for detecting more complex software problems and hardware vulnerabilities [8].

Conclusions

Proper implementation of microservices in microcontroller-based IoT systems can be more effective than traditional monolithic architecture. Microservices are more efficient in terms of security, reliability, and software development. However, since

the energy and computing power of microcontroller-based systems are exceptionally low compared to traditional computers, the direct application of microservices is not convenient. Therefore, in the research, a new approach for integration of microservices in microcontrolled based IoT systems is proposed and the framework for its application is defined. As proposed approach requires developing new container format for microcontrollers, security concerns related to it also explored and methods to reduce the security risks are discussed. This new approach allows for the effective implementation of microservices on microcontrollers with limited virtualization capabilities and resources, as well as fully preserving the functionality of the Internet of Things equipment of which it belongs.

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